

Effects of Mixed Mode and Collaborative Instructional Strategies on Biology Students' Performance and Interest in Imo State.

CHUKUNDAH Uchechi Doris, Ph.D

Department of Science Education
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

chukundahud@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies on biology student's performance and interest in Imo State. The research was carried out in Ehime-Mbano Local Government Area of Imo State. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental was adopted in the study, a total of 134 Biology students from three co-educational public senior secondary school were used via purposive sampling. Two instruments titled biology performance test on variation (BPTV) and Biology interest inventory on variation were developed, validated and considered reliable with Pearson product moment and Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.91 and 0.83 respectively. The research questions were answered with mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.5 level of significance using Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Results showed that mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy proved to be more effective than lecture method in the understanding of biology at the senior secondary school level. It also established that gender did not significantly influence academic performance of students. Furthermore, the study established that mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy are better interest motivators when applied in teaching biology. It is recommended that biology teachers should use mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy to teach biology and that Imo State Government should build and equip functional biology and computer laboratories in all the government co-educational schools and also train the teaches on how to use the digital tools for teaching and learning especially in the classroom.

Keywords: Mixed Mode, Collaborative, Instructional, Strategies, Biology, Students, Performance, Interest, Gender

Introduction

Biology plays vital role primarily in the explanation of complex life processes, structure functions, growth, starting point, evolution and spread of living species. Living organisms reveal ordered structures, being made up of a cell or cells, requires energy to survive or sustain existence, possibility to reproduce and to expand. Biology offers a comprehensive, scientific understanding of the interactions between all living and non-living things. Students who take the course gain knowledge about their bodies, resources, and possible environmental hazards. This indicates that the topic has to do with human existence. A major responsibility for the preservation and well-being of all living things is implied by the biological sciences. In the Biology curriculum document of Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) (FRN, 2014), it was stipulated that biology should be taught in a way that will help the students acquire adequate laboratory skills and relevant knowledge in the subject. Chukundah and Alibo (2024) maintained

that lack or total absence of instructional simulation material contributes significantly to high failure rate in science subjects.

Interestingly, the study of biology in the recent times has gained high level of interest among the under-graduate students due to its relevance in Neuroscience, Biochemistry, Anatomy, Pharmacy, Physiology and others. One of the major goals of education is to produce literate citizens who have acquired the appropriate skills for the development of themselves and the society. Education is an instrument for national development and social change (FRN 2014). It maximizes the creative potentials and skills of the individual for self-fulfillment and general development of the society. The aspect of education that involves the teaching of scientific principles and generalizations to the individuals of the society which aims at making them become scientifically literate citizen is referred to as science education (Agwo, 2016). Science education is strongly rooted in sciences, scientific literacy is the ability to make well informed decisions and choices based on the possession of a basic core and cognitive awareness of scientific facts, ideas, realities, principles and theories as well as the possession of fundamental technical skills in sciences (Ali, 2015). This implies therefore, that the general goal of science education is to develop scientifically literate citizens with the necessary intellectual resources, values, attitudes and inquiry skills to promote the development of man as a rational human being capable of critical thinking (Salami, 2015).

Accordingly, the future of any nation in term of science and technology depends ultimately on the performance of students in science (Aluko, 2016). Science subjects are taught at the secondary school level to help students continue in science related courses at higher institutions. According to Ibekwu (2015), science and technology is the pivot upon which national development revolve. The need to expose students to strategies that will involve their active participation in learning biology necessitated an investigation into the effectiveness of mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies in improving senior secondary school student's performance and interest in biology. Mixed mode instructional strategy involves a combination of digital instruction and one – on – one face time instruction. Students can work on their own with new concepts which make room for teachers to circle and support individual students who may need individualized attention, and zeal or interest to learn. Interest is an important variable in learning because when one becomes interested in an activity he or she is likely be more deeply involved in that activity: interest is an attribute associated with the affective domain of taxonomy of educational objectives. We must not lose sight of gender. Gender is an important extraneous variable which sometimes affects the academic performance of students. This is probably because most students at the secondary school level are between the ages of 14 to 19, which is the age bracket when most of them are used as service givers both in school and at home. It is also the age most students drop out of school due to poverty and distractions. There is therefore the need to use teaching strategies that encourage gender equality, positive interdependence and group work so as to motivate the students for higher academic performance. (UNESCO, 2014) gender equality is the main objective a teacher achieves using mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies because of their characteristics strategies or features.

Ali et al., (2021), conducted investigation on the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on mathematics achievement of fifth grade students. The experiment was conducted at the government school in District Swat Pakistan using pre-test post-test comparative group design on 64 students in two groups control and experimental. The result showed that collaborative instructional strategy has a positive effect on students' academic achievement. Chukundah and Alibo (2024) investigated the utilisation of instructional simulation in effective teaching and

learning of sciences in secondary schools in Ekeremor Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, descriptive survey design was adopted, with a sample of 98 SSS3 science students drawn from 1224 senior secondary school students of entire 16 secondary schools in Ekeremor. Questionnaire was used for data collection. Findings revealed utilisation of graphic simulation, computer modelling and laboratory equipment. The study recommended holistic use of graphic simulation, computer modelling and laboratory equipment in teaching and learning of science.

Onu et al., (2020) conducted a study on improving Biology student's interest and achievement in Biology. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, which was conducted in obollo-for education zone, with the population comprising of 1,691 SSI biology students, and a sample of 200 students. The finding revealed that students taught using collaborative learning had better achievement and interest ratings than those taught with lecture method. Bulb (2017) studied the effect of mixed mode on students' performance in photosynthesis, 48 students participated in the study, and result was analysed using descriptive statistics. Result revealed that students generally preferred mixed-mode.

Mixed and collaborative instructional strategies have feature that shift focus primarily transmitting sciences facts through large lectures to engaging students in active learning in which gender roles are not visible. It encourages active participation of male and female students in group laboratory investigation, in and outside classroom search for knowledge. Both male and female students have equal opportunities in mixed mode instructional strategy. To achieve a good conceptual understanding of variation, there is need to apply the conceptual change principles by engaging the active involvement of the students in practical and field experience where the students will be knowledge builders instead of knowledge consumers. It can also encourage the development of the student's critical thinking and innovative attitudes for problem solving in the society.

Statement of the Problem

Low performance, in biology at the senior secondary certificate examination in Nigeria has become the major challenge of the time. The report of the chief examiners of the West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) on biology results at the national level the years 2021 and 2023 showed that the performance of biology students in 2022 was slightly poor with a raw score of 31 and standard deviation of 11.92 when compared with the raw mean score of 31 and the standard deviation of 10.91 of WASSCE 2020. Moreover, studies have reported low academic performance in biology in different point of the country Onwukwo and Akuezuilo (2014). The 60%: 40% Provision for Science/Technology and Arts/Humanity admission ratio into higher institutions in Nigeria is not being maintained because of low academic performance in biology and other science subjects at the WAEC and Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) by candidates. There is need to continue to search for better ways of teaching biology in order to improve student academic performance at both internal and external examinations and realize the nations educational objectives. Low performance in biology has been the trend in most schools in Imo State specifically Ehime-Mbano as exemplified by the WAEC results.

The percentage passes score above D7 for most of the years have been extremely poor. This persistent low performance in biology results is a major challenge affecting securing admission into tertiary institutions especially for the study of sciences. This has led to low man power and economic development. There is therefore an urgent need to find solution to this, challenge in biology. Against this backdrop, this study tends to ascertain whether mixed mode and collaborative

instructional strategies when used in teaching and learning biology would improve the students' performance and interest in secondary schools.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to determine the effect of mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies on biology student's performance and interest in Ehime-Mbano Local Government Area of Imo State. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Ascertain the effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the student's mean performance score in Biology.
2. Examine the effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on students mean interest score of student in Biology.
3. Compare the effects of mixed mode, collaborative instructional strategies and lecture method on the male and female students mean performance score in Biology.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the students' mean performance score in Biology?
2. How does effect of mixed mode instructional strategy affect the students mean interest score in Biology?
3. What is the difference between the effect of mixed mode, collaborative instructional strategies and lecture method on the male and female students mean performance score in Biology?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses in null form were formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the mean performance score of students in biology.
- H₀₂: There is no significant effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the mean interest score of student in biology.
- H₀₃: The effects of mixed mode, collaborative instructional strategies and lecture method do not differ significantly on the mean performance score of male and female students in biology

Methodology

The following sub-headings were used: Research design, population of the study, sample and sampling techniques, research instrument, validity of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, method of data collection and method of data analysis.

Research Design

The study adopted quasi- experimental design specifically, a pre-test, post-test experimental and control group design was used to determine the effect of mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies on biology students' academic performance and interest in Imo State, Biology students in Ehime – Mbano Local Government Area to be precise formed the respondents. The students were not randomized. Thus, intact classes were used.

Population of the Study

The population for the study is made up of the entire six thousand, three hundred and two (6302) senior secondary school biology students in the twelve (12) public secondary schools in Ehime-Mbano, Imo State (Imo State Secondary School Board 2024).

Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample of 134 SSII students was drawn from two (2) intact classes of the two Imo State owned co-educational senior secondary schools. The two co-educational schools were selected using purposive sampling, technique based on the availability of biology laboratory, schools that have presented candidates for senior school certificate examination for at least three years and co-educational setting, while one intact SSII class was selected from each of the two schools and also assigned to experimental group 1 and 2 and control group using random sampling.

Research Instrument

Two instruments for data collation were used; The Biology Performance Test on Variation (BPTV) was developed and used for data collection. The BPTV comprised of 30 multiple choice objective questions drawn from the content area of the study variation. The biology performance test on variation (BPTV) was selected from West African Senior Secondary School based on the content of the study, and Biology Inventory on Variation (BIV) which was designed to evaluate the interest level of the students in variation concept in biology. Items on the inventory were scored on four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Strongly Disagree (2), and Disagree (1).

Validity of Instrument

The face and content validity of the BPTV was done with the help of two senior biology teachers who are experts from Department of Science Education, Federal University Otuoke. The corrections made were incorporated into the final version of the instrument. The lesson notes were also validated by biology teachers. Language clarity, appropriateness of scientific terms, coverage of the topics of the study, objectives stated being appropriate for the student's level were validated.

Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments were trial tested with 45 students in SS2 model secondary school Umualumaku, Ehime Mbano who were not part of the main study but found to be equivalent in every respect of the students that were used for the study. Items in BPTV that passed the difficulty and discrimination test were certified suitable for the students. While the reliability coefficient of BIV using Cronbach Alpha Reliability coefficient was calculated as 0.83 considered reliable enough for the study.

Administration of the Instrument

The Biology Performance Test on Variation (BPTV) and Biology Interest Inventory on Variation (BIIV) were administered as pre-test to both the experimental and control groups. The student in the experiment group were taught using mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies and control groups were taught using lecture method. The treatment was administered for four weeks. Immediately after four weeks of treatment, Biology Performance Test on Variation (BPTV) and Biology Interest Inventory on Variation (BIIV) were re-administered as post-test to measure the

students' learning outcomes of the two groups, their responses were graded and their scores obtained

Method of Data Analysis

The data analysis was done using descriptive statistics (Means) and standard deviation to answer the research questions. Hypotheses were tested and analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results Presentation

Research Question 1

What is the effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the students' mean performance score in biology?

Table 1: Mean performance scores and standard deviations of students taught biology with mixed mode instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method

Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)
Experimental	71	36.42	11.25	42.28	13.08
Control	63	33.29	10.53	35.66	10.89
Total	134				

The table shows the mean performance scores and standard deviations of students taught Biology using the mixed mode instructional strategy (experimental group) and the lecture method (control group). The experimental group improved from a pre-test mean score of 36.42 to a post-test mean score of 42.28, indicating a gain of 5.86 points. In contrast, the control group improved from a pre-test mean score of 33.29 to a post-test mean score of 35.66, with a smaller gain of 2.37 points. The higher mean gain and standard deviation in the experimental group suggest that the mixed mode instructional strategy had a more substantial and varied effect on students' performance compared to the lecture method.

Research Question 2

How does effect of mixed mode instructional strategy affect the students mean interest score in Biology?

Table 2: Mean Interest Scores and Standard Deviations of Students Taught Biology Using Mixed Mode Instructional Strategy and Lecture Method

Group	Number	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean Interest (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean Interest (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	
Experimental	71	40.32	8.14	46.89	10.58	6.57
Control	63	38.10	7.89	40.43	8.46	2.33
Total	134					

The table shows the mean interest scores and standard deviations of students taught Biology using the mixed mode instructional strategy (experimental group) and the lecture method (control group). The experimental group improved from a pre-test mean interest score of 40.32 to a post-test mean interest score of 46.89, with a mean gain of 6.57. The control group improved from a pre-test mean interest score of 38.10 to a post-test mean interest score of 40.43, with a smaller mean gain of 2.33. The higher mean gain in the experimental group suggests that the mixed mode instructional strategy had a greater positive impact on students' interest in Biology compared to the lecture method. The experimental group also exhibited slightly greater variability in interest scores post-test, as indicated by the increase in standard deviation.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between effects of mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategies and lecture method on the male and female students mean performance score in biology?

Table 3: Mean performance scores of male and female students in Biology across instructional strategies

Group	Gender	Number (N)	Pre-Test Mean Performance Scores (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (SD)	Post-Test Mean Performance Scores (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (SD)	Mean Gain
Mixed Mode	Male	32	35.50	10.82	43.75	9.54	8.25
	Female	39	37.25	11.12	45.32	9.87	8.07
Collaborative	Male	30	34.80	10.45	42.20	9.76	7.40
	Female	41	36.10	11.23	43.85	10.12	7.75
Lecture	Male	31	33.40	9.87	37.60	9.54	4.20
	Female	32	34.25	10.03	38.15	10.01	3.90
Total	Male	93	34.55	10.38	41.52	9.61	6.97
	Female	112	35.87	10.79	42.78	9.99	6.91

The table shows the mean performance scores of male and female students in biology across three instructional strategies: mixed mode, collaborative, and lecture methods. For the mixed mode strategy, males had a mean gain of 8.25, slightly higher than females, who had a mean gain of 8.07. Under the collaborative strategy, females achieved a mean gain of 7.75, which was slightly higher than the 7.40 mean gain for males. The lecture method produced the lowest mean gains for both genders, with males achieving 4.20 and females 3.90. Both male and female students performed better in terms of mean gains with the mixed mode and collaborative strategies compared to the lecture method. Female students outperformed males slightly in collaborative and lecture strategies, while male students showed a marginally higher improvement in the mixed mode strategy. The total mean gains were very similar between males (6.97) and females (6.91), indicating minimal gender differences in overall performance improvement.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the mean performance score of students in Biology.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance on the effect of mixed instructional strategy on the mean performance of students in Biology

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	252.22	2	126.11	10.61	.00	Rejected
Intercept	112.56	1	112.56	7.07	.00	
Pretest	211.59	1	211.59			
GROUP	106.65	1	106.65	11.02	.00	
Error	1114.08	132	8.44	16.42	.00	
Total	1797.10	134				
Corrected Total	1045.47	133				

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) results indicate that the mixed mode instructional strategy had a significant effect on students' mean performance scores in biology, as the group effect was statistically significant at $F(1,132) = 11.02, p = .00$. The null hypothesis (H_0), which stated no significant effect, was therefore rejected. The corrected model also revealed a significant result ($F(2,132) = 10.61, p = .00$), further confirming the impact of the instructional strategy. These findings suggest that the mixed mode instructional strategy significantly improved students' performance in Biology.

H₀2: There is no significant effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on the mean interest score of students in Biology.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on the effect of mixed instructional strategy on the mean interest score of students in Biology

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	222.16	2	111.08	8.44	.00	Rejected
Intercept	106.94	1	106.94	4.51	.00	
Pretest	198.43	1	198.43			
GROUP	89.73	1	89.73	9.46	.00	
Error	778.80	132	5.90	12.54	.00	
Total	1396.06	134				
Corrected Total	1101.03	133				

The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) in Table 5 revealed a significant effect of mixed-mode instructional strategy on the mean interest score of students in biology, as indicated by the F-value of 9.46 and a p-value of 0.00 for the GROUP variable. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, confirming a statistically significant effect. Additionally, the corrected model shows an F-value of 8.44 and a p-value of 0.00, reinforcing the significance of

outperform the lecture method in promoting deeper understanding and improved student achievement. The finding is in line with Bonk and Graham (2012) who posited that combining traditional and innovative teaching methods creates an inclusive and dynamic learning environment that fosters deeper understanding. Consequently, the mixed mode strategy has proven to be more effective than the lecture method in improving academic performance and promoting comprehensive student achievement.

On effect of mixed mode instructional strategy on students' mean interest score in biology, the findings of the study revealed that the mixed-mode instructional strategy had a significantly greater positive effect on students' interest in Biology compared to the traditional lecture method. This approach, which combines innovative and conventional teaching methods, was found to engage students more effectively, fostering a deeper connection to the subject matter. Consequently, students taught using the mixed-mode strategy demonstrated higher level of interest in Biology lessons than their counterparts exposed solely to the lecture method. The finding aligns with the work of Olusola and Rotimi (2020), who highlighted the effectiveness of mixed-mode instructional strategies in enhancing student engagement and interest in science subjects, including Biology. According to their research, this teaching approach leverages the strengths of both traditional and innovative methods, creating a more interactive and inclusive learning environment. Their study further demonstrated that students exposed to mixed-mode strategies not only showed increased enthusiasm for science subjects but also sustained higher levels of participation and curiosity throughout the learning process.

In considering differences among the effects of mixed mode, collaborative instructional strategies and lecture method on the male and female students' mean performance score in biology, the findings of the study revealed that both male and female students achieved higher mean gains when taught using mixed-mode and collaborative strategies compared to the traditional lecture method. Female students demonstrated a slight advantage over their male counterparts in both the collaborative and lecture strategies, indicating their stronger adaptation to these approaches. Conversely, male students exhibited a marginally higher improvement when exposed to the mixed-mode strategy, suggesting that this combination of innovative and conventional methods better aligns with their learning preferences and styles. Graham, Woodfield, and Harrison (2013) supported the assertion that mixed-mode instructional strategies enhance learning outcomes for both male and female students by addressing diverse learning preferences and promoting engagement. Their study emphasizes that blending traditional and innovative teaching methods creates a more flexible and inclusive learning environment, leading to improved performance across genders.

Conclusions

This study has shown that mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy remain one of the best for teaching of Biology at the Senior Secondary School level for better understanding and enhancement of students' academic performance.

There is gender equality in academic performance when mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy are used to teach biology.

Mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy remains better interest motivator when applied in teaching Biology compared to when lecture method is used.

Recommendations

Base on the findings, the following recommendation were made:

1. Biology teachers should use mixed mode instructional strategy and collaborative instructional strategy to teach Biology as to enhance the students' academic performance.
2. IMO state government should build and equip functional Biology and computer laboratories in all the government co-educational schools and also train the teachers on how to use the digital tools for teaching and learning in the classroom, thereby using the mixed mode and collaborative instructional strategy in building interest of their students.
3. Teachers should enrol, attend and participate in the science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) workshops and conferences to improve and update their knowledge in contemporary teaching methods, adopting mixed mode and collaborative instruction that gives equal opportunity to male and female students.

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